

Compact Custom Spring Joint for Series Elastic Actuators in Physical Human-Robot Interaction

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Abstract—In this paper, we discuss the design methodology of a novel torsional spring, embedded in a series elastic actuator (SEA) for portable upper-limb exoskeleton applications. We found out that a sine wave shape is the best compromise to achieve the desired compliance for a safe use of the exos. The spring was manufactured in a 3D-printed metal. Experiments have been performed on the SEA to validate the joint characteristic in the torque-angle plane. Results are promising since linearity is confirmed and the experimental stiffness coincides with the theoretical estimate. Therefore, the proposed elastic joint is suitable for integration in physical human-robot interactions.

I. INTRODUCTION

A large burden for wearable robotics is concerned with safe operation and robust force control while relieving muscle activity during arm elevation and weight-lifting operations [1]. In this regard, Series Elastic Actuators (SEA) [2] have been often endorsed in grounded exoskeletons and orthosis due to their inner capability to store and release elastic energy, thus avoiding impulsive interactions and achieving fine torque control [3].

Still, their integration in portable upper-limb exoskeletons is concerned by the compromise between the demanded torque and the compactness/lightweight requirements. Recent research contrived solutions to these limitations. Variable stiffness/impedance actuators provide compactness and real-time stiffness setting, but they may present complex mechanical structures [4]. Viscoelastic-based SEAs efficiently exploit the damping while preserving stability, at the expense of hysteresis and non-linear behavior [5]. Linear elements - like springs - does not always prevent the system from undergoing non-linearities [6], and although being cheap and commercially available, they are not versatile.

Custom-made springs are valuable candidates to ensure a mostly linear behavior and offer a completely versatile approach for portable exoskeletons. Nevertheless, there is no standard procedure for their designing, thus existing prototypes have been realized for high stiffness demand [7], reaching fewer than 10° of angular deflection at the nominal torque.

To address these issues, we present the design methodology for a SEA to be employed on the FLEXOS [8] portable shoulder exoskeleton. The objective of the design is to accurately measure a huge stroke of the actuator (15°) at the nominal torque of a commercial brushless DC motor, equal to 9 Nm.

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Fig. 1. The proposed metal spring for compact series elastic actuators.

The architecture of this system is an improved version of the design proposed in [9] where we used commercial linear springs.

II. DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The joint is composed of two 3D-printed metal springs with sine wave-shaped units (Fig.1), joined together to form an equivalent spring, as shown in the exploded view of Fig.2.

More in detail, our contribution is a rigorous design methodology for a SEA joint under encumbrance and weight requirements. Analysis was initialized by studying the hyperstatic problem of a simple element for which it is possible to attribute the straight beam model and it was demonstrated that the trend of the motor torque is linear with the width of the elastic element and cubic with the height of the section of the same, while stress is linear only with its height. Based on this consideration, several geometries have been considered for the springs. Lastly, compliance is introduced with more accuracy and detail through a FEM analysis, whose results, reported in Fig. 3, confirm that a sine-wave shape is the best compromise, between the respect of the desired compliance and the failure criteria, to achieve a functional point of 9 Nm with a rotational deflection of 13.75° (which is very close to the design objective) . Besides, the joint provides enough torque resolution for granting safe physical Human-Robot interaction (pHRI) during the intended application. Each spring has a lightweight - 0.17 kg - and compact size - 9 mm in width, 98 mm in diameter, the same as the motor.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND CONCLUSION

Through characterization experiment, a static test is pursued by steps. Starting from unloaded condition and increasing of 0.5° every step of the duration of 60 s, the joint is loaded

Fig. 2. Exploded CAD view of the SEA

(c)

Fig. 5. (a) Our previous SEA equipped with commercially available torsion springs and (b) our new SEA with custom-made metal 3d-printed springs. (c) The two devices are mounted on the FLEXOS exoskeleton for comparison.

Fig. 3. (a) Undeformed and deformed shape comparison, (b) maximum value of Von Mises' stress

rotating the outer ring respect the inner one. The torque-angle characteristic of the SEA joint is pictured in Fig. 4. In addition, there is a linear behaviour for negative angle, which is convenient for increasing the intervention range of the SEA, better dealing with impulsive loads.

The compliant element resulted in a more compact version - Fig. 5 (b) - of the previous SEA prototype - Fig. 5 (a) - already developed in our previous work [9]. Both of the devices present the same total weight of 0.5 kg and achieve the same performance in torque resolution. In addition, the proposed sine wave-shaped designed spring is linear in the whole angle range compared to the nonlinear characteristic of the previous design. Both the solutions are shown in Fig. 5 (c) as mounted on the same FLEXOS exoskeleton to highlight compactness differences.

Fig. 4. Result of the experimental static characterization.

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